

Techno-Economic analysis of an Air-Source Heat pump system integrated with Phase change material for Decarbonising Residential Buildings in the United Kingdom

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Abstract

Air source heat pumps (ASHPs) are increasingly deployed in the United Kingdom as a low-carbon alternative to conventional gas boilers for residential heating. However, large-scale deployment of ASHPs may contribute to increased peak electricity demand during winter operation, resulting in higher operational costs and additional pressure on electricity networks. This study investigates the integration of thermal energy storage with ASHP systems, incorporating latent heat storage using phase change materials (PCM) and sensible heat storage (SHS) using water. A detached residential building under UK temperate climatic conditions is modelled to evaluate the performance of ASHP-LHS i.e. PCM and ASHP-SHS systems, compared with a standalone ASHP and a gas boiler. A comprehensive techno-economic and environmental assessment is conducted, including energy consumption, levelised cost of heating (LCOH), and carbon emissions. The results show that for the model scenario, ASHP-SHS and ASHP-LHS systems reduce energy consumption by 21.62% and 33.23%, respectively, compared to a standalone ASHP. The LCOH decreases from £0.122/kWh (gas boiler) to £0.1012/kWh for the ASHP-LHS system. Carbon emissions are reduced from 4.94 tCO₂/year (gas boiler) to 1.46 tCO₂/year for ASHP-LHS. The findings demonstrate that integrating thermal energy storage has the entailed to significantly improves heat pump performance, offering a cost-effective and low-carbon solution for residential heating in the United Kingdom.

Keywords

Heat Pump; thermal energy storage; techno-economic; Phase change material; Carbon emissions; time of use tariff

1 Introduction

Global energy demand is increasing due to population growth and urbanization, with buildings accounting for approximately 40% of global energy consumption [1]. In the United Kingdom, residential space heating represents a major share of building energy use, highlighting the need for low-carbon heating technologies to achieve Net Zero targets [2,3]. Air source heat pumps (ASHPs) are considered a promising alternative to conventional gas boilers due to their high efficiency and low carbon emissions [4]. However, their performance is limited by high peak electricity demand and operational costs [5]. Integrating thermal energy storage (TES), including sensible heat storage (SHS) and phase change materials (PCM), can improve operational flexibility, reduce peak demand, and enhance system efficiency [6,7].

Previous studies have mainly focused on the thermal performance of PCM-integrated heat pump systems [8-13], while comprehensive techno-economic and environmental assessments under UK climatic conditions remain limited. Therefore, this study investigates the performance of ASHP systems integrated with sensible heat storage (HP-SHS) and latent heat storage (HP-LHS) i.e PCM for residential buildings in the United Kingdom. The systems are compared with conventional gas boilers and standalone ASHP systems through energy, economic, and environmental analysis.

1.1 Literature Review

Previous studies have investigated the integration of heat pumps with thermal energy storage (TES), particularly phase change materials (PCMs), to improve operational flexibility, reduce peak electricity demand, and minimise heat pump cycling [6]. TES enables thermal energy generated during off-peak periods to be stored and later used for space heating.

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Several studies have demonstrated the benefits of PCM-integrated heat pump systems. Marzougui et al. [10] reported significant reductions in energy consumption and improvements in coefficient of performance (COP) using PCM storage. Sun et al. [11] and Hu et al. [12] also observed improved thermal storage capacity and operational performance in PCM-based systems. In addition, studies by Li et al. [14], Du et al. [15], and Ouhammou et al. [16] highlighted the potential of advanced PCM materials and TES configurations for reducing energy consumption and operational costs. Despite these developments, most previous studies have mainly focused on thermal and energy performance, while limited research has investigated the combined techno-economic and environmental performance of heat pump systems integrated with sensible heat storage (SHS) and PCM under UK climatic conditions and time-of-use (TOU) tariffs.

Therefore, this study investigates the techno-economic and environmental performance of ASHP systems integrated with sensible heat storage (HP-SHS) and latent heat storage (HP-LHS) i.e. HP-PCM, for residential buildings in the United Kingdom.

1.2 Objective of the Study

This study presents a comprehensive energy, economic, and environmental assessment of standalone ASHP, HP-SHS, HP-LHS, and conventional gas boiler systems for a residential building in London, United Kingdom, under TOU tariff operation.

The main objectives are:

- To develop a dynamic simulation framework for residential heating systems using EnergyPlus.
- To compare the energy performance of ASHP, HP-SHS, HP-LHS, and gas boiler systems.
- To evaluate economic feasibility using LCOH and payback period analysis.
- To analyse carbon emissions associated with the investigated systems. To provide a comprehensive 3E (energy, economic, and environmental) assessment of PCM-integrated heat pump systems for low-carbon residential heating.

2 Methodology

The heating systems investigated were dynamically modelled using EnergyPlus [17], which enables transient simulation of building energy systems under varying operating conditions. The model incorporated UK weather data, building construction properties, occupancy schedules, and internal heat gains from occupants, lighting, and electrical appliances. Figure 1 presents the integrated modelling framework of the residential building and associated heating systems.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the study

A detached two-storey residential building located in London, United Kingdom, with a total floor area of 186 m² was selected for the analysis. The building geometry was developed in SketchUp and imported into EnergyPlus as shown in Figure 2. The thermal properties of the building envelope were defined using multi-layer construction assemblies, while occupancy schedules and internal heat gains were based on CIBSE TM59 guidelines. An infiltration rate of 0.5 ACH was assumed throughout the simulations. The key thermophysical properties of the building envelope and internal heat gains are considered as per the CIBSE standards.

Figure 2. A model of the Detached house

The heating systems investigated included a conventional gas boiler, standalone air source heat pump (ASHP), heat pump integrated with sensible heat storage (HP-SHS), and heat pump integrated with latent heat storage i.e. phase change material storage (HP-LHS). The gas boiler and ASHP capacities were selected according to the building heating demand, with capacities of 20 kW and 16 kW, respectively. A heating setpoint range of 19–22 °C was applied across all thermal zones using proportional–integral (PI) control. The ASHP systems operated under a time-of-use (TOU) tariff strategy, where thermal energy was stored during low-tariff periods and discharged during peak periods.

For the HP-SHS system, a water-based storage tank was used for sensible heat storage, whereas the HP-LHS system utilised RT-42 paraffin wax for latent heat storage. A supply water temperature of 45 °C and source-side temperature of 10 °C were assumed for all heat

pump systems. Since direct PCM integration is not available in EnergyPlus, the ice thermal storage module was adapted using the thermophysical properties of RT-42 PCM, summarised in Table 1. A simulation timestep of 1 min was adopted to capture the transient operation of the heating and thermal storage systems. A simulation timestep of 1 min was adopted to accurately capture the transient operation of the heating and thermal storage systems. The energy, economic, and environmental performance metrics were evaluated using 15-minute aggregated simulation outputs consistent with the TOU tariff analysis.

Table 1: Thermophysical properties of the phase change material (PCM) paraffin wax (RT-42) used in the EnergyPlus model

Parameters	Values
Melting temperature	42 °C
Latent heat of fusion	190 kJ/kg
Density	890 kg/m ³ (Solid), 770 Kg/m ³ (Liquid)
Thermal conductivity	0.21 W/mk
Specific heat	2.1 kJ/kg.k

2.1 Economic and environmental analysis

The economic performance of the investigated systems was evaluated using levelized cost of heating (LCOH), net present value (NPV), and payback period (PBP). In addition, the environmental performance was assessed using annual carbon emissions and marginal abatement cost (MAC). These indicators enabled comparative techno-economic and environmental assessment of the investigated residential heating systems under UK climatic conditions.

2.1.1 Levelised Cost of Heat (LCOH)

The LCOH represents the average cost of heat generation over the system lifetime and is calculated as:

$$\frac{\sum \left[\frac{Capital_t + O\&M_t + Fuel_t + Carbon_t}{(1+r)^t} \right]}{\sum \left[\frac{Q_t}{(1+r)^t} \right]} \quad (1)$$

where:

- C_t is the total cost in year t (£), including capital, operation, and maintenance costs,
- Q_t is the useful heat delivered in year t (kWh),
- r is the discount rate,
- N is the system lifetime (years)

2.1.2 Net Present Value (NPV)

The net present value is used to evaluate the financial viability of each heating system over its lifetime:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} - C_0 \quad (2)$$

where:

- C_t represents the net cash flow in year t ,
- C_0 is the initial investment cost,

- r is the discount rate.

A positive NPV indicates that the investment is economically viable, while a negative value suggests otherwise.

2.1.3 Payback Period (PBP)

The simple payback period is used to estimate the time required to recover the initial investment:

$$PBP = \frac{C_0}{\text{Annual Net Savings}} \quad (3)$$

where annual net savings are defined as:

$$\text{Annual Net Savings} = \text{Energy Cost Savings} - \text{Annual Operating Cost}$$

This metric indicates investment risk and liquidity.

2.2 Environmental analysis

The environmental performance of the heating systems is evaluated based on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions associated with energy consumption.

2.2.1 Annual Carbon Emissions

Annual CO₂ emissions are calculated as:

$$CO_2 = E \times f \quad (4)$$

where:

- E is the annual energy consumption (kWh),
- f is the emission factor (kgCO₂/kWh) for electricity or natural gas.

Electricity emission factors correspond to the UK grid, while natural gas emission factors are based on standard combustion values.

2.2.2 Marginal Abatement Cost (MAC)

The marginal abatement cost (MAC) quantifies the cost-effectiveness of carbon emissions reductions achieved by transitioning from conventional gas boiler systems to low-carbon heating technologies. It represents the cost per unit of CO₂ emissions avoided and is calculated as:

$$MAC = \frac{C_{system} - C_{boiler}}{CO_{2,boiler} - CO_{2,system}} \quad (5)$$

where:

- C_{system} is the total cost of the alternative system
- C_{boiler} is the total cost of the gas boiler system,
- $CO_{2,boiler}$ and $CO_{2,system}$ are the corresponding annual emissions (tCO₂/year).

3 Validation of the Multi-Zone Modelling Approach

The developed EnergyPlus model was validated through literature benchmarking against a previously published model of the David Wilson Eco Home at the University of Nottingham [2]. The modelling framework incorporated building envelope properties, occupancy schedules, internal heat gains and heating control strategies under UK climatic conditions. The adopted approach was further benchmarked against Kutlu et al. [18], who investigated a solar-assisted heat pump

system with PCM storage at the same case-study building. Good agreement in heating demand and system performance trends confirmed the reliability of the modelling approach. Although direct experimental calibration was not conducted, the use of validated modelling assumptions and comparison with previous studies provides confidence in the results.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Meeting the heating demand of the residential Building with a gas boiler

The conventional gas boiler, modelled with a thermal efficiency of 90%, was used as the baseline heating system. The results showed that the system maintained indoor temperatures within the control range of 19–22 °C during occupied periods. For the selected winter period, the maximum heating load reached approximately 19.53 kW. The highest monthly heating demand occurred during winter, reaching 4531 kWh in January and 4494 kWh in December, while negligible heating demand was observed between May and September, as shown in Fig. 3. The annual natural gas consumption for space heating was approximately 24,225 kWh, indicating the substantial heating energy requirement associated with conventional boiler-based residential heating under UK climatic conditions.

Figure 3: Energy (Gas) consumption of space heating by Gas Boiler throughout the year

4.2 Meeting the heating demand of residential Building with the ASHP

The ASHP was operated under a time-of-use (TOU) tariff strategy, with operation scheduled during lower-cost tariff periods. The system maintained acceptable indoor thermal comfort; however, a temporary reduction in indoor temperature occurred during the peak tariff period when the heat pump was switched off. The ASHP system required approximately 9,381 kWh of electricity annually to satisfy the same space heating demand that required approximately 24,225 kWh of natural gas consumption in the conventional boiler system, as shown in Fig. 4. This reduction in final energy consumption is primarily

attributed to the higher efficiency of the heat pump system and improved operation under favourable ambient conditions.

Figure 4. Energy (Gas) consumption by Gas Boiler and electricity by ASHP under TOU tariff throughout the year

4.3 Meeting the heating demand of residential Building with the HP-SHS

The HP-SHS system utilised a water-based thermal storage tank to store thermal energy during low-tariff periods and discharge it during heating demand periods. The system maintained indoor temperatures generally between 20 °C and 22 °C. The annual electricity consumption of the HP-SHS system was approximately 7,302 kWh, representing a 21.62% reduction compared with the standalone ASHP system, as shown in Fig. 5. This improvement demonstrates the effectiveness of sensible heat storage in shifting heat pump operation towards low-tariff periods and reducing peak electricity demand.

Figure 5. Energy (Gas) consumption by Gas Boiler and electricity by ASHP and ASHP-SHS throughout the year

4.4 Meeting the heating demand of residential Building with the HP-LHS

The HP-LHS system utilised RT-42 paraffin wax for latent heat storage. Compared with the HP-SHS system, the PCM storage unit provided improved heat retention and more stable indoor temperatures. The annual electricity consumption of the HP-LHS system decreased to approximately 6,263 kWh, representing a 33.23% reduction compared with the standalone ASHP system, as shown in Fig. 6. The improved performance is mainly attributed to the

higher thermal energy storage density of the PCM, reduced heat pump cycling, and smoother system operation.

Figure 6. Energy (Gas) consumption by Gas Boiler and electricity by ASHP, ASHP-SHS and ASHP-LHS i.e. PCM throughout the year

4.5 Economic analysis

The economic analysis was conducted using levelized cost of heating (LCOH), present worth, annual savings and payback period. Without subsidy support, the LCOH was £0.122/kWh for the gas boiler, £0.105/kWh for the ASHP, £0.1153/kWh for the HP-SHS system and £0.1012/kWh for the HP-LHS system. The HP-LHS system achieved the lowest heating cost due to its reduced electricity consumption and improved storage performance.

With the UK Boiler Upgrade Scheme subsidy of £7,500, the LCOH values decreased to £0.0792/kWh for the ASHP, £0.0921/kWh for the HP-SHS system and £0.0785/kWh for the HP-LHS system as shown in figure 7. The subsidy significantly improved the economic feasibility of heat pump systems by reducing capital investment and shortening payback periods.

Figure 7: Levelized cost of heat with subsidies for different heating system in detached house Building

4.6 Environmental analysis

The annual carbon emissions, calculated using 2024 UK grid electricity and natural gas emission factors with 15-minute operational data resolution, decreased from 4.94 tCO₂/year for the gas boiler system to 2.18 tCO₂/year for the ASHP, 1.71 tCO₂/year for the HP-SHS system, and 1.46 tCO₂/year for the HP-LHS i.e. PCM system, as shown

in Fig. 7. The HP-LHS system achieved the lowest emissions due to its lower electricity consumption and improved operational efficiency.

Figure 7: Carbon emissions of different heating system in the detached house

The marginal abatement cost values were -304.19 £/tCO₂ for the ASHP, -317.03 £/tCO₂ for the HP-SHS system and -342.54 £/tCO₂ for the HP-LHS system as shown in figure 8. The negative values indicate that the heat pump-based systems reduce emissions while also providing economic benefits compared with the baseline gas boiler system.

Figure 8: Marginal Abatement cost analysis of the different heating systems in detached residential Buildings

5 Limitations of the Work

This study involves several modelling assumptions. Occupancy schedules and internal heat gains were based on CIBSE TM59 guidelines and may not be directly applicable to other regions or household behaviours. External shading, internal blinds, curtains, natural ventilation and occupant window-opening behaviour were not considered, which may slightly affect the predicted heating demand. In addition, direct PCM storage integration for heating applications is not available in the standard EnergyPlus library; therefore, the ice thermal storage module was adapted using the thermophysical properties of RT-42 paraffin wax. Although this approach provides a reasonable representation of PCM storage behaviour, future work should include experimental validation.

6 Conclusion

This study assessed the energy, economic and environmental performance of ASHP systems integrated with sensible heat storage and PCM-based latent heat storage for a detached residential building in London. The results showed that annual heating energy consumption decreased from 24,225 kWh for the gas boiler to 9,381 kWh for the standalone ASHP, 7,302 kWh for the HP–SHS system and 6,263 kWh for the HP–LHS system.

The HP–LHS system achieved the best overall performance, reducing energy consumption by 33.23% compared with the standalone ASHP. It also achieved the lowest LCOH of £0.1012/kWh without subsidy and £0.0785/kWh with subsidy support. Carbon emissions decreased from 4.94 tCO₂/year for the gas boiler to 1.46 tCO₂/year for the HP–LHS system, while the marginal abatement cost reached –342.54 £/tCO₂.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that PCM-integrated heat pump systems offer strong potential for low-carbon residential heating in the United Kingdom. Future work should focus on experimental validation, PCM storage design optimization and evaluation across different UK building typologies.

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